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Exploring fault propagation and the role of inherited structures during caldera collapse through laboratory experiments

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Abstract

Caldera collapse received large attention during the last decades and was widely studied using various approaches, spanning from field-geology to numerical and analogue modelling. Analogue models allow to reproduce caldera collapse deformation, providing information otherwise difficult to obtain during such an extremely transient geological process. A wide range of analogue studies is available in literature, nonetheless, some aspects are still barely known, particularly the propagation of caldera faults and the role of inherited structures during caldera collapse. We have thus addressed the above research questions through analogue models. Our models show how calderas may experience asymmetry due to the lateral propagation of caldera-related faults. Furthermore, inherited discontinuities may affect caldera collapse by inducing rectilinear caldera faults that generate non-circular ring faults. Finally, sub-vertical discontinuities may be able, in specific conditions, to inhibit the formation of standard caldera structures that have been commonly observed in previous experimental series (i.e., early inward-dipping reverse faults followed by peripheral normal ring faults). Our models were then compared with four natural examples (the Acoculco and Los Humeros caldera complexes in Mexico, the Tuscolo-Artemisio caldera in the Colli Albani volcanic district, Italy and the Glencoe Caldera in Scotland), suggesting a relevant control exerted by inherited faults during caldera collapse. On the basis of the modelling results, we propose an evolutionary model that can be generalized and likely applied to many other caldera settings worldwide.

1. Introduction and aims of the study

Collapsed calderas are circular to subcircular large depressions originating from the subsidence induced by depletion and/or migration of magma from a shallow or deep reservoir during eruptions (e.g., Williams, 1941; Druitt & Sparks, 1984; Lipman, 1997). These eruptive events can produce from few up to $>5000 \text{ km}^3$ of magma, leading to depressions with diameter ranging between few to many tens of kilometres, and a subsidence varying from meters up to kilometres (e.g., Druitt & Sparks, 1984; Lipman, 1984, 1997). Caldera collapse can be associated with lava flows (e.g., the 2014-2015 Bárðarbunga collapse and the 2018 Kilauea summit eruption and collapse; Gudmundsson et al., 2016; Neal et al., 2019; Sigurdsson 2019), and/or with paroxysmal explosive eruptions. Caldera development can be associated with any geodynamic context (e.g., Geyer & Martí, 2008), with magmatism spanning from mafic to felsic (e.g., Acocella, 2007, and references therein). The regional and local tectonic setting can further influence caldera collapse due to a variety of possible stress field conditions.

Regional faults may interact with caldera structures influencing collapse evolution, which is generally accommodated by (inward-dipping) normal and (outward-dipping) reverse faults variously located with respect to the caldera rims (e.g., Walker, 1984; Roche et al., 2000; Cole et al., 2005; Kusumoto & Takamura, 2005; Geyer, et al., 2006; Acocella, 2007; Gudmundsson, 2007; Geyer & Martí, 2014). Incipient outward-dipping reverse faults, first demonstrated by Clough et al. (1909) at the Glencoe Caldera (Scotland), start to develop at the magma chamber margin, then propagate upward and are infilled by magma fluids to accommodate volume changes inside the magma chamber (Anderson, 1936; Martí et al., 1994; Branney, 1995). Afterwards, deformation may shift to peripheral areas that experience normal faulting, and generate the most external ring faults bounding the depression (e.g., Sanford 1950; Branney, 1995; Martí et al., 1994; Roche et al., 2000; Acocella, 2007). In this process, the volcano-tectonic structures may interact with pre-existing regional structures generating different patterns of deformation and possibly resulting in different and specific caldera collapse evolution (e.g., Cailleau et al., 2003; Acocella et al., 2004; Holohan et al., 2005, 2008a).

Therefore, understanding the mutual relationships and the possible influence of structural inheritance on caldera collapse, as well as how faults propagate both vertically and laterally, is crucial to understand caldera collapse processes. A correct understanding of these aspects is also critical for many applications, particularly for geothermal exploration since caldera collapse-

related structures, able to facilitate the ascent of hydrothermal fluids (e.g., Martí et al., 2008; Giordano et al. 2014; Garden et al. 2017; Liotta and WP4 Working Group, 2019; Montanari et al. 2017a; Jentsch et al., 2020), may interact with inherited structures. However, the volcano-tectonic fault pattern in relatively recent caldera collapses is often difficult to investigate at surface, due to volcanic deposits that infill and often drape the caldera morphology (e.g., WoldeGabriel et al., 1990, 1992; Le Turdu et al., 1999), while ancient eroded collapses may show the caldera structures and, in some favourable cases due to exposure condition (e.g., the Glencoe Caldera in Scotland), the involvement of regional faults in accommodating portion of the collapsed calderas (e.g., Moore & Kokelaar, 1998). Furthermore, due to the quasi-instantaneous nature of explosive caldera collapse, field-work can only allow to investigate the post-deformation structural setting, while the direct and in-depth monitoring of caldera collapse is difficult, yet nowadays not impossible.

In this perspective, laboratory analogue modelling enable us to reproduce and continuously monitor this process, representing a valuable tool for integrating the field data, and for this reason it has been widely used through years (see Ancella, 2007 and Geyer & Martì, 2014 and reference therein). After presenting a short literature overview of analogue modelling and describing the analogue modelling methodology adopted in this study, we show 13 models (quantitatively analysed through high resolution digital elevation models and digital particle Image velocimetry), testing the role of pre-existing structures interacting with a collapsing caldera. We compare our models with four natural examples (the Acozulco and Los Humeros caldera complexes in Mexico, the Tuscolo-Artemisio caldera edifice in the Colli Albani volcanic district, Italy and the Glencoe Caldera in Scotland). On the basis of the results of laboratory experiments, we aim to provide new insights into the role of inherited structures during caldera collapse and to propose an evolutionary model that can be generalized and applied to caldera settings worldwide.

2. Analogue modelling of caldera collapse: a brief overview of the possible approaches

Several modelling approaches are known in the literature, and apply either overpressure or underpressure mechanisms to reproduce collapsed calderas. The first mechanism implies overpressure increase inside a magma chamber, leading to superficial tumescence and therefore creating the condition for tensile stress and caldera collapse initiation. This mechanism has been applied to analogue models using various techniques spanning from balloon inflation into a sand package, to silicon and rigid spheres intrusion into granular material (e.g., Komuro, 1984; Martì et

al., 1994; Walter and Troll, 2001; Acocella et al., 2001a; Troll et al., 2002, Acocella and Mulugeta, 2002). Underpressure experiments commonly reproduce caldera collapse initiation through removal of a viscous fluid simulating magma from an experimental magma chamber (using various tools, e.g. mechanical piston, rubber bladder), therefore triggering a pressure drop in the magma chamber roof (e.g., Acocella et al., 2000; Roche et al., 2000; Acocella et al., 2001b; Belousov et al., 2005; Holohan et al., 2008b; Burchardt & Walter, 2010; Ruch et al., 2012; Coumans & Stix, 2016). Balloon deflation in granular materials has been used to reproduce underpressure mechanisms as well (e.g., Walter and Troll, 2001; Troll et al., 2002; Kennedy et al., 2004; Lavelle et al., 2004; Geyer et al., 2006). Analogue models using the underpressure mechanism have been also used to investigate the role of regional stress and inherited structures on caldera collapse evolution (e.g., Cailleau et al., 2003; Acocella et al., 2004; Holohan et al., 2005, 2008a). Our modelling belongs to the last branch of studies (i.e., underpressure mechanisms). In particular, we aim to investigate how caldera faults propagate and how single or multiple inherited structures in the proximity of the magma chamber may, or may not affect the development of structures typically observed inside collapsed calderas.

3. Methods

3.1. Experimental setup, procedure and analogue materials

In our physical experiments, we built a perfectly cylindrical magma chamber (12 cm in diameter and 2 cm thick, created by shaping a chamber in a plaster base filled with the magma analogue) that was placed at the base of a 6 cm-thick sand pack reproducing the pre-volcanic brittle overburden (Fig. 1a). Coloured millimetre-sand horizons were sieved with a regular vertical spacing of 1 cm and used as passive markers to visualise internal deformation once the model was cut. Each model was built in a Plexiglas box and the magma chamber was drained from a central circular hole placed at its base. We constantly monitored the volume of drained analogue magma. We simulated the magma with pure vegetable Polyglycerine-3 (PG3; see Montanari et al., 2017a; 2020), while the sedimentary cover consisted of a mixture of Quartz sand (Fontainebleau sand, provided by Sibelco Italia S.p.A.) and Potassic-feldspar sand (K-feldspar superfine sand, produced by AKW Kaolin) mixed with a 70:30 proportion in weight (Montanari et al., 2017b; Del Ventisette et al., 2019).

During caldera collapse, we drained 65% of the magma-analogue (PG3) in all experiments, to guarantee model comparison. Furthermore, this value led to an average caldera subsidence of 1.5-

2 cm, which, once scaled, corresponds to plausible values of 1.5-2 km in nature (see section 3.3 below). Initially, we used a basic setup, represented by a circular magma chamber and an undeformed overburden (Fig. 1a). This setup was used as a “control model” for the others. Afterwards, we introduced various inherited discontinuities (hereinafter referred to as ID) in different positions to simulate inherited fabrics within the brittle overburden (i.e., “overburden discontinuities”; Fig. 1b). We produced IDs in the overburden by cutting the sand pack with a blade fixed onto an adjustable glide that allows varying depth and inclination of the cuts (Fig. 1e).

Figure 1. Setup of caldera collapse models. (a) Simple caldera collapse (SCC). (b) Overburden-discontinuity caldera collapse (ODCC). (c) Substrate-discontinuity caldera collapse (SDCC). (d) Substrate to overburden-discontinuity (SODCC). (e) Cartoon illustrating the apparatus used to produce cuts into the sand pack, mimicking inherited discontinuities (ID). Note that in (b-e) the setup shows only one sub-vertical discontinuity in the substrate and/or overburden, but other models were also designed with two sub-vertical orthogonal discontinuities, or 60° inward/outward dipping discontinuities.

This operation causes re-orientation of particles and variation in their compaction, generating a sharp and narrow millimetric-wide weak zone, which focuses deformation during model development if favourably oriented with respect to the local stress field (e.g., Bellahsen & Daniel, 2005; Maestrelli et al., 2020a). We then varied the shape of the magma chamber by imposing one

or two straight sides, simulating pre-existing fault discontinuities, from now on called “substrate discontinuities” (Fig. 1c). In a fourth series, we combined overburden and substrate IDs (Fig. 1d). At the end of the deformation, models were saturated with water, frozen and cross-sectioned for investigating the 3D caldera fault pattern. We checked reproducibility of results by replicating the models a few times (at least 2 per model). Overall, our experimental series includes 13 models, subdivided into 4 sub-series (Figs. 1 and 2). An open-access database of the models (Maestrelli et al., 2020b) used in this work is available at http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4084639_and specifically described, together with the detailed methodology, in Maestrelli et al. (2021).

3.1.1. Simple caldera collapse model setup (SCC)

The basic setup (Fig. 2a) represents a reference model that consists of a cylindrical analogue magma chamber (12 cm in diameter and 2 cm thick) placed at the centre of the Plexiglas box. The rims of the chamber are designed vertical. It is worth noting that no pre-caldera volcanic edifice was simulated in our setup.

3.1.2. Overburden-discontinuity caldera collapse model setup (ODCC)

We modified the SCC setup to investigate the role of overburden ID during caldera collapse. Vertical discontinuities were introduced at specific locations by cutting through the sand package (Fig. 2b). We tested different ID geometries in the sand pack, specifically (1) an ID in a near-tangential internal position (≈ 1 cm) to the analogue magma chamber, (2) an ID in a tangential position, (3) an ID above the centre of the magma chamber, and (4) an ID in a near-tangential external position (≈ 1 cm).

Figure 2. Model setup for the four performed experimental series. (a) Standard caldera collapse (SCC setup) with no IDs. (b) Overburden-discontinuity (ODCC), consisting of four models with a circular magmatic chamber and a brittle discontinuity in the overburden located (1) in a near-tangential (≈ 1 cm, ODCC-1), (2) tangential (ODCC-2), (3) central (ODCC-3) and (4) external (≈ 1 cm, ODCC-04) positions. (c) Substrate-discontinuity (SDCC), consisting of four models showing one (SDCC-1) or two (SDCC-2) rectilinear and vertical sides of the analogue magmatic chamber, mimicking structures bounding the magma chamber in nature. The series also consists of two models built with a single, 60°-dipping rectilinear inward- and outward- sides (SDCC-3 and SDCC-4). (d) Four models (SODCC-1 to SODCC-4) performed with the substrate to overburden-discontinuity setup (SODCC); this setup is similar to SDCC, but also contains a vertical and inward/outward 60°-dipping brittle discontinuities.

3.1.3. Substrate-discontinuity caldera collapse model setup (SDCC)

This model setup was designed to reproduce the presence of inherited fabrics in the substrate (i.e. at the depth of the analogue magma chamber, below the overburden layer), controlling the geometry of the magmatic chamber but not crosscutting the overlying brittle overburden. We simulated the ID by introducing one or two rectilinear sides to the magmatic chamber depending on the model. The straight “faults” were built with a sub-vertical attitude, and afterwards as discontinuities dipping 60°, both inward and outward (Fig. 2c).

3.1.4. Substrate to Overburden-discontinuity caldera collapse model setup (SODCC)

In comparison to the former one, this setup aims to investigate the role of ID crosscutting both the substrate and the overburden. Starting from the SDCC setup, we introduced a straight discontinuity in the sand pack in continuity with the discontinuity in the substrate (i.e. the rectilinear side bounding the analogue magma chamber) to reproduce the role of a continuous, single inherited fault. We reproduced one or two IDs intersecting at 90°, and dipping 90° (i.e., vertical) and 60° inward/outward (Fig. 2d).

3.2. Monitoring and analysis of deformation

All the performed models were monitored with an automated top-view camera acquisition system (shooting interval of 120 seconds), in order to reconstruct the chronology of model deformation and the 2D geometry. Furthermore, we acquired the final 3D topography (digital elevation model, DEM) through photogrammetry (i.e., the *Structure from motion* method, using Agisoft Photoscan® software; e.g., Donnadieu et al., 2003, Schönbberger & Frahm, 2016), used to analyse caldera morphology and to extract slope attribute using a GIS software. The latter measures the dip of caldera surfaces and is therefore used to highlight caldera structures (as they represent breaks-in slope). The morphology of the subsided central caldera piston is extracted from DEMs and used to highlight the degree of tilting of the piston block: we define here the Relative Depth (RD) which is the normalized topography (shown as depth map) of the subsided block, with the zero value indicating the highest point of the block. Top-view images were used to implement Digital Particle Image Velocimetry (DPIV) analysis of models, which were in turn used to quantify the horizontal component of deformation. This makes the analyses less sensitive to the vertical motions that are normally associated with caldera subsidence. Specifically, DPIV analysis was used to extract maps of velocity vector magnitude and strain rate. The strain rate is the velocity gradient in the direction of the local velocity and it is defined as follows:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} \quad (1)$$

The analysis was performed using the *PIVlab* algorithms developed by Thielicke and Stamhuis (2014) for *MATLAB*TM, which allows the quantitative and qualitative analysis of particle flow by calculating particle displacement vectors over the model surface between photographic frames. The DPIV analysis was performed using couple of frames with 360 seconds time steps. The DPIV

algorithm (FFT window deformation) uses an iterative process set with a 3-Pass search window (Pass 1: Interrogation area 64 px; Step: 32 px; Pass 2: Interrogation area 32 px; Step: 16 px; Pass 3: Interrogation area 16 px; Step: 8 px). All other settings were kept as set by default.

3.3. Model scaling

The models were scaled down to nature (Ramberg, 1981) following the assumptions and procedure reported in Montanari et al. (2017a). Materials and scaling parameters are summarized in Table 1. We set a length scaling ratio l^* of 10^{-5} (l^* being the ratio l_m/l_n , where l_m is the length in the model and l_n is the length in nature), so that one centimetre in the model scales to 1 kilometre in nature. This scaling value is a suitable ratio to investigate model structure at the resolution of interest, and fits well with the dimensions of many caldera systems worldwide. Furthermore, such a length ratio implies a depth for the magma source in nature of 6 km, a plausible (average) value for many caldera settings (e.g., Roche & Druit, 2001; Geyer et al., 2006; Verma et al., 2011; Geshi et al., 2014; Brothelande & Merle, 2015; Brothelande et al., 2016; Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2018). Models were run in natural gravity, so that g^* (the scaling ratio between gravitational acceleration in the model and in nature) is equal to 1. The use of Qz/K-feldspar sand mixture yields a material density (ρ_m) of $\sim 1408 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, which implies a scaling ratio for density ρ^* of ~ 0.5 when considering a natural rock density (ρ_n) of $\sim 2810 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. A similar density scaling ratio can be obtained for magma, considering PG3 as analogue magma ($\rho_m \sim 1280 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) and a natural magma with $\rho_n \sim 2500\text{-}2200 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The latter is a density representative of an andesitic to rhyolitic magma at $\sim 1000 \text{ C}^\circ$ (Murase & McBirney, 1973), which is likely to occur in many caldera settings. From the length and density scaling ratios we can obtain the stress scaling ratio as follows:

$$\sigma^* = \rho^* g^* l^* \approx 5 \times 10^{-6} \quad (2)$$

In order to correctly scale the velocity (V) of caldera collapse, we applied the approach used by Holohan et al. (2008b). Specifically, the viscosity scaling ratio for magma ($\eta^* = \eta_m/\eta_n$) can be expressed as follows:

$$\eta^* = \sigma^* T^* \quad (3)$$

where $T^* = T_m/T_n$ is the scaling ratio for time, which is function of the velocity and length scaling ratio:

$$V^* = l^* / T^* \quad (4)$$

Viscosity of natural magmas varies over a wide range, spanning from 10^2 Pa s (for basaltic magmas) up to 10^{15} Pa s (for acid magmas with large amount of crystals) (Merle, 2015, and reference therein). Considering a viscosity (η_m) of 17 Pa s for the PG3 analogue magma (Montanari et al., 2017a, 2020) and an average value of 10^8 Pa s for the natural magma (η_n), from equations (3) and (4) it follows that:

$$V^* = l^* \sigma^* / \eta^* \quad (5)$$

and therefore we calculate a velocity ratio $V^* = 2.94 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Using our reference model (SCC-1) we can extrapolate a velocity of collapse (V_m) of 0.5 cm h^{-1} (i.e., $1.39 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, obtained considering a maximum subsidence of 1.5 cm occurred over 3 hours of model deformation) and a scaled velocity of natural collapse (V_n) of $\approx 4.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, corresponding to $\approx 400 \text{ m day}^{-1}$. This value is in line with the velocity range proposed for several historic caldera collapses. In particular, the La Reunion Volcano accumulated $\approx 450 \text{ m}$ of maximum subsidence over two days (i.e., average $V_n = 225 \text{ m day}^{-1}$) during the 2007 basaltic eruption, while the 1912 Katmai Rhyolite eruption caused a collapse of $>1300 \text{ m}$ over a time span of three days (i.e., average $V_n \approx 430 \text{ m day}^{-1}$), but higher and lower values are also reported for other calderas (Gudmundsson et al., 2016 and references therein). The velocity value obtained for our laboratory experiments is therefore similar to documented natural velocities, hence supporting that our models are correctly scaled.

Analogue & scaling parameters	Material	Physical Parameter	Model	Nature	Model/nature Scaling ratio
Brittle layer	Qz/K feldspar sand mixture (70:30 % wt)	Density (ρ), kg m^{-3}	1408	2800	$\rho^* = 0.5$
		Internal Friction Coefficient (μ)	0.83	0.6-0.85	$\mu^* \approx 1$
		Cohesion (c), Pa	10	$\sim 10^7$	$c^* \approx 10^{-6}$
Analogue magma	Polyglycerine-3 (PG3)	Density (ρ), kg m^{-3}	1280	2200-2500	$\rho^* \approx 0.5$
		Viscosity (η), Pa s	17	10^8	$\eta^* = 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$
Geometric and dynamic scaling parameters		Length (l), m	0.01	1000	$l^* = 10^{-5}$
		Gravity (g), m s^{-2}	9.8	9.8	$g^* = 1$
		Stress (σ), Pa	14	2.8×10^{-6}	$\sigma^* = 5 \times 10^{-6}$
		Velocity of collapse (V), m day^{-1}	1.39×10^{-6}	≈ 400	$V^* = 2.94 \times 10^{-4}$

Table 1. Summary of material and scaling parameters

3.4. Model limitations

The analogue modelling approach generally implies several assumptions, which are necessary to approximate the variability of every natural system. In the case of caldera collapse, this approach allows to isolate and investigate specific aspects of the process, but implies some limitations that need to be considered when comparing the modelling results with nature. Specifically, our models approximate the magma chamber to a simple cylindrical shape bearing a rigid boundary, implying standardized caldera collapse dimension and shape. The crust is simulated by a homogenous sand mixture which is cut to create discontinuities, the latter simulating discrete faults in nature rather than pervasive fractured volumes or larger weak zones. Finally, analogue models are not able to reproduce magma-rock interaction due to chemical and thermal effects, as well as the effect of volatile exsolution or temperature-dependent magma parameters. Therefore, the thermo-mechanical behaviour of natural magmatic systems is approximated in our models to a purely mechanical behaviour.

4. Modelling results

4.1. Description of models

We present here below the description of top views, cross sections as well as slope and RD maps extracted from DEMs (Figs. 3-9) for the selected models.

4.1.1. Simple caldera collapse models (SCC)

Model (SCC-1) was built with the standard setup described above and contained no IDs (Figs. 1a and 2a). The model showed an incipient caldera collapse characterised by a down-sag phase (Fig. 3a, T_1), where inner faults became visible at surface in discrete locations and then propagated laterally (Fig. 3a, T_2). Before the inner faults intersected each other, most of the deformation shifted to peripheral areas to create the caldera ring faults (Fig. 3a, T_3). The latter emerged at multiple locations (implying multiple points of nucleation at depth) and from there propagated laterally (following a clockwise or anticlockwise trajectory) and finally connected (Fig. 3a, T_4) to “close” the caldera ring faults. Meanwhile, the inner faults proceeded in their lateral propagation, and then intersected forming an “x-pattern” (black dashed rectangle in Fig. 3b) to finally connect to the ring peripheral faults (Fig. 3a, T_5). The result of this process (Fig. 3b, c) was a near-symmetric

caldera collapse (inclination of the subsided central caldera piston $\approx 1^\circ$; see RD and slope maps and profile in Fig. 3c, d) with two dip orientation of major faults, particularly inner and outer faults that were revealed by model cross sections to be outward-dipping reverse faults and inward-dipping normal faults, respectively (Fig. 3e). Both inner and outer faults linked at depth terminating in the proximity of the edge of the experimental magma chamber (Fig. 3e).

Figure 3. (a) Top view evolution of Model SCC-1. After incipient central subsidence (T₁), reverse faults started to develop and to propagate laterally (T₂), and then linked with ring normal faults that shifted the deformation outwards (T₃). After the linkage (T₄), the ring-faults accommodated caldera subsidence (T₅). (b) Final top view photograph (superimposed onto a DEM) (c) Structural interpretation of caldera structures and Relative Depth (RD) map and profile of the central subsided caldera piston. Depth contours (red lines) are spaced 1 mm. The black dashed rectangle in (b) highlights the “x-pattern” of faults formed by the intersection of the laterally propagating inner outward-dipping reverse faults. Thin dashed lines in (c) indicate slope debris. (d) Slope analysis used to highlight caldera structures and the dip of caldera portions. (e) Cross sections A-A' and B-B', whose trace is indicated in (b). The area highlighted in red below the caldera indicates the remnant of PG3 fluid that was not extruded during the caldera collapse process.

4.1.2. Overburden-discontinuity caldera collapse models (ODCC)

In this experimental series (Fig. 2b), we tested the effect of a single ID placed at various locations within the analogue overburden. In model ODCC-1 (Fig. 4a), the ID is located in an inner, nearly-tangential position with respect to the analogue magma chamber (≈ 1 cm from the rim). The ID was promptly reactivated as a sub-vertical normal fault during caldera collapse, and at 50% of deformation it appeared as a straight fault in top view (Fig. 4a). Its reactivation was contemporaneous to the formation of the inner reverse faults and preceded the surfacing of the inward-dipping normal ring-faults (that link to the ID). Despite its incipient reactivation, the ID did not act as a long-term barrier for ring-fault propagation, since peripheral ring faults kept on propagating in their circular trajectory, forming a well-ounded caldera depression. The sub-vertical attitude of the ID and its incipient reactivation formed a morphological plateau with a sharp structural margin, subsided with respect to the caldera margins (see the topographic profile the DEM in Fig. 4a, cross section b-b' in Fig. 7b and the slope map in Fig. 8a). Furthermore, the collapsed block acquired several degrees of tilting (see RD map in Fig. 9a) and the majority of deformation was accommodated by the reverse fault at the caldera margin opposite to the ID location.

A similar development and geometry of structures are observed in model ODCC-2 (Fig. 4b), where the ID is tangential to the analogue magma chamber edge. In this case, the superficial manifestation of the ID reactivation was smoother, and its morphologic evidence was less defined (i.e., the ID is shorter and acquires less throw; see the slope map in Fig. 8b) as a result of its more external position with respect to the model ODCC-1. For this reason, we also observed less interaction with the system of inner outward-dipping reverse faults, which were able to develop better and finally intersect each other forming the “x-pattern” of faults. The RD map for this model shows the tilting of the caldera piston ($\approx 5^\circ$, see RD in Fig. 9b). In the last two models of this experimental series no reactivation of the ID was observed. Model ODCC-3 (Fig. 4c) was set with a central ID, which showed no signs of reactivation both in incipient and advanced deformation phases (Fig. 4c), resulting in symmetric caldera structures collapse with an asymmetric collapsed caldera piston (Figs. 8c and 9c). The topographic profile in Figure 4c shows that almost no tilting was induced on the piston during the collapse process. Model ODCC-4 was designed with an external, near-tangential ID (located ≈ 1 cm from the magma chamber edge; Figs. 4d and 8d),

which did not affect the caldera collapse, showing no relevant signs of reactivation. A small curvilinear fault branch departing from the ring fault and located in correspondence to the ID position was observed, but then it was aborted during the final collapse stages, and was likely a result of lateral unload due to the formation of the ring faults that may have triggered the slight reactivation of the ID. However, it had no direct effect on the caldera collapse process. The subsided caldera piston showed $\approx 5^\circ$ of tilting (see RD map and profile in Fig. 9d)

Figure 4. Caldera collapse models incorporating discontinuities into the overburden (a) Model ODCC-1, (b) Model ODCC-2, (c) Model ODCC-3 and (d) Model ODCC-4. From top to bottom: models at 50% of deformation and 100% of deformation, DEM with topographic profiles and line-drawing of surface deformation.

4.1.3. Substrate-discontinuity caldera collapse models (SDCC)

This third experimental series (Fig. 2c) tested the role of ID bounding only the analogue magma chamber (i.e., not crosscutting the overlying brittle sand pack). In Model SDCC-1 (Fig. 5a), we introduced one ID acting as a sub-vertical boundary for the analogue magma chamber. Its presence did not produce any alteration in the chronology of fault pattern development, which proceeded with the formation of the inner outward-dipping reverse faults and subsequent migration of the deformation toward the peripheral areas and the consequent formation of the inward-dipping normal faults. Despite these similarities with the standard model SSC-1, the reactivation of the ID forced the above-mentioned faults to follow a rectilinear trajectory. The result was a caldera depression with the inner collapsed piston delimited by a rectilinear outward-dipping reverse fault, and a roughly rectilinear caldera rim in correspondence of the ID, as the faulting in the peripheral area was freer to assume a form closer to the idealised cylindrical or conical shape (Figs. 5a and 8e). The subsided caldera piston showed a tilting close to 10° as highlighted by the slope map (Fig. 8e) and by RD analysis (Fig. 9e). A similar structural pattern was observed in Model SDCC-2 (Fig. 5b; cross section c-c' in Fig. 7c), which was designed with two orthogonal IDs. Interestingly, in both models the inner collapsed block appeared connected with the external ring faults by the development of short curvilinear reverse faults (see line-drawings in Fig. 5a,b). Model SDCC-2 resulted in a less tilted caldera piston block (Figs. 8f and 9f).

Models SDCC-3 and SDCC-4 (Fig. 5c,d) reproduced the setup of model SDCC-1 but varied the dip-angle of the ID. In particular, Model SDCC-3 simulated an inward-dipping (60°) inherited discontinuity, while Model SDCC-4 was built with an ID with an outward-dipping (60°) discontinuity. No first-order variations in the evolution of the structural caldera pattern were observed, and both models showed few degrees of tilting ($<3^\circ$) of the piston block (Figs. 8g,h and 9g,h). Overall, all the four models resulted in "piston-like" caldera collapse, with slight tilt of the subsided block and one/two rectilinear caldera rims. Notably, no consistency was observed between the dip direction of the slightly tilted piston block and the position of the IDs.

Figure 5. Caldera collapse models incorporating discontinuities in the substrate. (a) Model SDCC-1, (b) Model SDCC-2, (c) Model SDCC-3 and (d) Model SDCC-4.

4.1.4. Substrate to Overburden-discontinuity models (SODCC)

The last experimental series (Fig. 2d) tested the effect of an ID including both the substrate (i.e., bounding the analogue magma chamber) and the overburden, therefore combining the setups of ODCC and SDCC models. Model SODCC-1 (Fig. 6a), developed an incipient reactivation of the single ID as normal fault, to which both the inner outward-dipping reverse faults and the outer inward-dipping normal faults connected (Figs. 6 and 8i). This model resulted in a near-symmetrical collapsed piston block ($<2^\circ$; Fig. 9i). An identical evolution was observed in model SODCC-2 (Fig. 6b and cross section d-d' in Fig. 7d; Fig. 8j), in which two IDs were introduced. The collapsed piston

block showed several degree of tilting ($>5^\circ$, Fig. 9j) and both models did not develop any reverse fault in the proximity of the ID, where all deformation was accommodated by the reactivation of the latter structure as a normal fault.

Figure 6. Caldera collapse models incorporating discontinuities that include both the substrate and overburden. (a) Model SODCC-1, (b) Model SODCC-2, (c) Model SODCC-3 and (d) Model SODCC-4.

Models SODCC-3 and SODCC-4 (Fig. 6c,d), designed with an inward and outward 60° -dipping ID, respectively, show a different evolution. In particular, these models developed a standard pattern of structures: in the case of a dipping structure (60°), both reverse and normal faults formed, and the ID did not accommodate the whole deformation. For this reason, the evolution of these two models was equivalent to that of models SDCC-3 and SDCC-4 (Fig. 5c,d). Furthermore, the two latter models showed a lesser influence of the ID(s) due to their outward and inward dip, which

caused the propagating ring faults to reactivate the ID in shorter segments. Finally, both models resulted in almost no tilt of the subsided piston block ($<2^\circ$; Figs. 8k,l and 9k,l).

Figure 7. DEM superimposed on top-view photographs for models (a) SCC-1, (b) SDCC-1, (c) ODCC-1 and (d) SODCC-1, together with cross-sections showing the effect of the IDs on the structural deformation pattern at the end of caldera collapse.

Figure 8. Slope analysis of the selected models. Slope maps highlight caldera structures and the inclination of caldera sectors. Slope angles range between 0° (horizontal surface) and 90° (vertical surface).

Figure 9. DEM-based analysis showing the Relative Depth (RD) of the subsided central caldera piston, highlighting its inclination: depth values are normalized to the sole topography of the piston (i.e. the zero value represents the highest topographical point of the piston). Red lines represent contours of depth (1 mm equal spacing). RD profiles, sampled along the dip direction of the subsided piston block, show their average inclination.

4.2. DPIV analysis

DPIV analysis has been performed on all models to quantitatively analyse the deformation pattern resulting from caldera collapse and the interaction with the IDs. The Velocity Magnitude attribute illustrates the velocity of tracked particles obtained with the DPIV analysis, which has been first

applied to Model SCC-1 revealing some relevant aspects of model deformation. At the very early stages of deformation, where faulting was not visible at surface yet, DPIV highlights the incipient down-sagging above the analogue magma chamber, as indicated by centripetal velocity vectors (Fig. 10a). This broad area of deformation corresponds to the dimension of the underlying analogue magma chamber. Deformation then localized in the inner portion and the down-sagging area and became more restricted (Fig. 10b,c), since the reverse faults became visible at surface (Fig. 10d). The incipient inner reverse faults then propagated laterally following a circular trajectory until deformation shifted again (as highlighted by colour gradient in Figure 10e) and localized in the peripheral areas. As a consequence, normal faults started to develop and became visible at surface and then propagated laterally (Fig. 10f,g). Since these new-born faults have accommodated some deformation, the velocity vectors indicated a “strain jump” to the opposite side of the collapsing caldera (Fig. 10f-i), where another normal fault nucleation point appeared at surface (Fig. 10j). As the earlier normal fault, the latter fault propagated laterally and linked with the former to complete the outer ring faults which progressively increased their throw, accommodating the caldera subsidence in these final deformation stages (Fig. 10k-o). Nonetheless, during the advanced stages of deformation, not all the strain was accommodated by the normal ring faults. As highlighted by Velocity Magnitude (Fig. 10h-o), part of the deformation was still accommodated by the inner reverse faults that kept on propagating laterally to finally intersect and link with the peripheral ring faults. Such an intersection created the x-pattern of faults shown by the dashed black rectangle in Figure 3a. This implies that the inner reverse faults do not completely deactivate once deformation shifts to the more peripheral areas.

Figure 10. DPIV analysis performed on Model SCC-1, showing the velocity vectors of deformation on model surface (see colour scale for reference). The deformation range is the percentage of deformation that corresponds to the interval analysed through DPIV (0% and 100% are the onset and the end of caldera collapse). The time step represents the temporal interval between two images used in the DPIV analysis and is 360 seconds for each couple of frames. Black arrows indicate actual vectors, while white arrows represent interpolated vectors.

This effect is well documented by the simple strain rate derivative parameters (see Equation 1) obtained through the DPIV analysis (Fig. 11), which clearly marks where and when strain was accommodated by specific structures.

Strain analysis also indicates that, despite a final near-symmetrical caldera collapse (not only in top view but also in cross section, in which the collapsed block is near-horizontal; Fig. 3e), this geometry is acquired through steps of asymmetric fault propagation (Fig. 11d-f) and “strain jumps” (Fig. 11h-j). Furthermore, strain analysis also highlights the occurrence of some strike-slip fault movements coincident with the x-pattern of inner reverse faults (black arrows in Fig. 11m-o).

Velocity magnitude obtained for models of series ODCC, SDCC and SODCC (Fig. 12) highlights the role of the ID in controlling caldera collapse during the early stage of deformation, when strain shifts from the inner outward-dipping reverse faults to the normal inward-dipping ring faults. For models ODCC-1 and ODCC-2, the ID acts as a temporary barrier for ring fault propagation (Fig. 12a,b), while in Model ODCC-3, DPIV highlights no influence of the central ID (Fig. 12c), and only minor effects of the external ID in model ODCC-4 (Fig. 12d).

Conversely, the barrier effect is evident from DPIV analysis applied to models of SDCC series, where velocity fields delimited by one or two rectilinear boundaries are visible (Fig. 12e to h). This effect was permanent and the rectilinear sides were maintained during the entire collapse process. A similar process also occurred in models of series SODCC (Fig. 12i to l).

Figure 11. Simple strain rate derivative obtained from DPIV analysis of Model SCC-1. Reddish colours indicate strain accommodated along E-W direction (taking the top of the photos as the reference for N), bluish colours indicate strain along a N-S trend, while greenish colours correspond to zero strain (see colour bar). The black arrows indicate faults with significant strike-slip component of movement.

Figure 12. DPIV analysis performed on model of series SDCC, ODCC and SODCC. Despite the DPIV analysis was performed for the whole model development, it is shown here only the analysis of convenient frame couples that highlight specific effects of the IDs in each model. Black arrows indicate actual vectors, while white arrows represent interpolated vectors. The velocity magnitude of selected frame couples together with the range of deformation are shown for each model. Setting parameters are as described in Figure 10.

5. Discussion

5.1. Fault architecture, propagation and the role of inherited structures

With the standard setup (model SCC-1), outward reverse faults were the first to develop, propagating upward from the boundary of the analogue magma chamber. Deformation was afterward accommodated by normal faults, propagating from the surface and linking at depth with the reverse faults. This evolutionary model is at the first order in line with the results highlighted by many underpressure experiments (e.g., Roche et al., 2000; Acocella et al., 2001b; Geyer et al., 2006; Holohan et al., 2008b; Liu et al., 2019) and summarized in a conceptual model by Acocella (2007; cf. Figs. 19 and 21). Nonetheless, some of the above mentioned analogue models were

performed using a slightly different setup that includes a rigid subsiding piston (e.g., Acocella et al., 2004; Liu et al., 2019) to induce the collapse of various analogue magma materials (silicone/honey). Using a rigid piston has clear advantages (e.g., model reproducibility), but it may also limit the structural variability inside the models, as the collapse is driven by the mechanical movement of the piston and not directly by the analogue magma flow. Furthermore, the use of a less viscous analogue material (such as the PG3 used in this study) can better reproduce the “natural” development of the process. In fact, in our models the gravity-driven outflow of the analogue magma allowed for the “self-accommodation” of volumes inside the collapsing caldera, which reached the maximum subsidence through steps of asymmetric propagation. This aspect is similar to what documented in models by Roche et al. (2000) and Molohan et al. (2008b), which are characterised by lateral fault propagation of the inner reverse faults and outer normal faults during model collapse. As in the above mentioned studies, in our models incipient faults nucleate randomly, and then propagate laterally (Fig. 13a,b) until reformation shifts to peripheral areas (Fig. 13c).

Figure 13. Conceptual model showing standard model evolution in the absence of IDs (inspired to Model SCC-1 and similar to the one proposed in Acocella, 2007). Top panels show deformation stages seen in top-view photos while middle and lower panels illustrate the temporal development and lateral propagation of the major faults in 2D and 3D, respectively. The red dot indicates the nucleation point for reverse faults, while the green dot marks the same

points for normal faults. The last column on the right illustrates the formation of the x-pattern of faults, which is in agreement with the occurrence of strike-slip movements.

Our models show that inner reverse faults do not deactivate and continue to accommodate part of the strain associated with caldera roof collapse, proceeding in their lateral propagation to finally intersect forming an x-pattern of faults (Fig. 13d). Similar splaying structures were already described in models with a roof thickness/diameter ratio ≈ 1 (e.g., Roche et al., 2001; Holohan et al., 2013). Inner caldera faults deriving from this lateral propagation show some strike-slip components of movement, as shown by strain analysis (Fig. 11m-o) and also by the results of Holohan et al. (2013). Holohan et al. (2013) and Bathke et al. (2015) suggest that strike-slip components of motions specifically arise because of centripetal shortening and/or asymmetric (off-centred) collapse. The latter leads to a concurrent bulk translation of the fault-bound roof, which is partly accommodated by strike-slip faulting. This testifies that caldera collapse is not accommodated by vertical strain only (i.e., by reverse and normal faults), but lateral fault propagation accompanied by strike-slip components may also contribute, even in the absence of a favourable regional stress field, as already shown by previous studies (Holohan et al., 2013; Bathke et al., 2015).

Reference model SCC-1 depicted a piston-like caldera collapse (Figs. 3, 7a, section a-a' and 14a), from which the above described evolutionary model (similarly to the model summarized by Acocella, 2007) can be traced out (Fig. 13). This model shows that the collapse is, at first order, near-symmetric, both in plain-view and in cross section, with the formation of concentric outward-dipping reverse faults and inward-dipping normal faults. This pattern may show slight variations when an ID is introduced in the brittle overburden.

Despite the role of inherited crustal structures during caldera collapse was proposed for several natural cases (e.g., the Silent Canyon caldera complex in Nevada, the Rotorua Caldera in New Zealand and Ischia in Italy, Ferguson et al., 1994; Milner et al., 2002; Acocella & Funicello, 1999; Cole et al., 2005), the specific role of these structures was only partly addressed by analogue modelling (Cailleau et al., 2003; Acocella et al., 2004; Holohan et al., 2005, 2008a), and we aimed to systematically investigate this issue through our experimental series. Specifically, the ODCC models (Fig. 4) have shown that an internal ID does not show any sign of reactivation during the collapse, in line with what proposed by other Authors (Holohan et al., 2008a; Acocella et al., 2004). External IDs do not have any major effect on the caldera structural pattern, while tangential and near-tangential IDs strongly influence caldera collapse by creating rectilinear faults inside the

subsiding area, connecting the caldera ring faults (Figs. 7b, section b-b' and Fig. 14b). Despite this, the overall caldera setting remains symmetric, with circular caldera rims. Different is the case of a collapsed caldera that interacted with one or more IDs delimiting the analogue magma chamber, such as in series ODCC. The presence of such a discontinuity strongly affects the final shape of the caldera, which shows rectilinear inner reverse faults and outer normal faults in correspondence of the ID (Fig. 7c, section c-c' and Fig. 14c). Nonetheless, the final structural patterns are still characterised by the presence of both reverse and normal faults in correspondence of the ID, a characteristic that has not been observed in case of a caldera interacting with discontinuities delimiting the analogue magma chamber in the substrate and crosscutting the overburden (Series SODCC). The incipient reactivation of such sub-vertical discontinuities inhibits, in fact, the formation of the inner outward-dipping reverse faults, and the reactivated structures massively accommodate the strain produced during caldera collapse on that side (Fig. 7d, section d-d' and Fig. 14d). Interestingly, a similar behaviour was observed by Holohan et al. (2008a; cf. with their Fig. 9d). This behaviour is instead not observed in the presence of a 60°-dipping ID, even though both reverse and normal faults develop showing a rectilinear attitude in plan-view. These results are in line with what already observed by Holohan et al. (2005, 2008a) and Acocella et al. (2004).

A final consideration worth to be mentioned is that the presence/absence of IDs does not seem to exert a major control on the degree of tilting of the subsided caldera piston block, which does not show unequivocal correlations with the presence/position of inherited structures (see Figs. 8 and 9).

In many caldera systems, eruptive deposits associated with the caldera collapse and post-collapse activity may mask morpho-tectonic features, draping the reliefs and hiding both regional and caldera structures (e.g., WoldeGabriel et al., 1990, 1992; Le Turdu et al., 1999). It is therefore of primary importance to evaluate the possibility that inherited structures - besides constraining the geometry of the caldera collapse inducing the formation of sub-vertical and rectilinear ring faults - can also locally inhibit the formation of intra-caldera structures in some sectors (e.g., segments of outward-dipping reverse faults that may be missing), as shown by some of our models and in agreement with Holohan et al. (2008a).

Figure 14. Summary sketch showing end member models from each experimental series with (a) no ID, (b) an internal near-tangential ID in the overburden, (c) an ID delimiting the analogue magma (substrate ID), and (d) an ID delimiting both the analogue magma chamber and crosscutting the overburden (substrate to overburden ID). The upper panels (a-d) show the final model top-view photos, while middle and bottom panels show the 2D (a₁-d₁) and 3D (a₂-d₂) deformation pattern resulting from caldera collapse.

5.2. Comparing results with natural systems

5.2.1. Los Humeros and Acozulco caldera systems

The Los Humeros (LH) volcanic complex and the Acozulco (AC) caldera complex (Puebla state) are located in the south-eastern sector of the Trans-Mexican Volcanic Belt (TMVB), a NW-SE trending large-scale (>1000 km) volcano-tectonic feature extending through central Mexico (Fig. 15a,b). This volcanic belt is considered to be the result of the progressive Rivera and Cocos slabs subduction, tearing and sinking below the North America plate, a process able to induce the upward migration of hot material from the asthenosphere and the consequent magma emplacement at crustal levels (e.g., Pardo & Suárez, 1995; Ferrari et al., 2004; 2012). In the TMVB, inherited structures have been interpreted to be reactivated and interact with Miocene-

Quaternary faults and have likely localized eruptive centres (Garduño-Monroy et al., 2009; Gómez-Vasconcelos et al., 2020; Maestrelli et al., 2020a).

At the local scale of LH and AC (Fig. 15c,d) inherited structures are represented by $\approx N45^\circ$ and $\approx N140^\circ$ trending regional faults (Campos-Enriquez & Garduño-Monroy, 1987; Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2017; Avellán et al., 2019; García-Palomo et al., 2018; Maestrelli et al., 2020a), which may have played a role during the development of the caldera complexes and likely during caldera collapse (Bonini et al., 2021). As noted earlier, caldera-related structures, may interact with inherited discontinuities and localise the up-flow of geothermal fluids, thereby representing important exploration targets (Giordano et al., 2014; Norini et al., 2015). The Los Humeros and Acoculco were in fact the focus of the GEMex Project that aimed to push forward the development of Superhot Geothermal Systems (SGS) and Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS) at the two sites. Our analogue models can contribute to the investigation of these issues.

Los Humeros volcanic complex

The LH volcanic complex (Fig. 15a,c) is the result of a multiphase volcanic activity (Ferriz and Mahood, 1984), which led to the final collapse of the LH caldera and the secondary nested Los Potreros caldera (LPC, Fig. 15c). The older LH caldera (dated at 164 ± 4.2 ka; Cavazos-Alvarez & Carrasco-Núñez, 2020) is a 18×15 km wide depression, whose collapse is associated with the emplacement of the Xaltipan ignimbrite (115 km^3 dense rock equivalent DRE; Ferriz and Mahood, 1984; recently revised to 265 km^3 by Cavazos-Alvarez & Carrasco-Núñez, 2020), followed by a second caldera collapse responsible for the eruption of the Zaragoza ignimbrite (15 km^3 DRE) and the formation of the smaller (9×10 km-wide) nested LPC (Fig. 15c) dated at 69 ± 16 ka (Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2018). This secondary caldera depression is located close to the western margin of the LH caldera, which is marked by the presence of a \sim NW-trending alignment of eruptive centres likely in correspondence of the rectilinear LH caldera ring fault (Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2017). Interestingly, this alignment (and therefore the caldera ring fault) is coincident with the trend of regional structures and is roughly orthogonal to the trend of the SE caldera margin, striking NE-SW (i.e., the Los Humeros Scarp, Fig. 15c), in agreement with other regional structural trends (e.g., Norini et al., 2019). This structural setting may suggest that the LH caldera collapse was partly controlled by existing regional structures (Liotta and WP4 Working Group, 2019; Maestrelli et al., 2020a), and it is therefore possible to compare this caldera complex with our analogue models.

Despite the complex structural setting of the LH caldera due to the presence of the smaller LPC with its caldera resurgence radial fault pattern (Norini et al., 2019; Bonini et al., 2021), the outer morphology of the LH caldera can be compared with models from both the SDCC and SODCC series. This implies that the caldera may have been controlled by magma chamber-bounding structures in the substrate or by inherited structures located in the substrate and extending through the overburden. Such near-surfacing structures (likely sealed by volcanic products) therefore represent inherited discontinuities (i.e., substrate to overburden ID). Due to the complex setting related to the LPC presence and the sealing by ignimbrite deposits, it is difficult to establish the presence and geometry of inner structures. We compare the LH caldera with models with both a single ID and two IDs, since the NW-SE-trending caldera rim has no clear morphological evidence except for the eruptive centre alignment (Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2017, Fig. 15c).

Hypothesizing only a single rectilinear inherited discontinuity, we compare the LH caldera with models SDCC-1 and SODCC-1 (Fig. 15e,f). The structural pattern of the outer ring fault is similar to what is observed at the LH caldera, with its NE-SW trending southeastern margin bounding the collapsed caldera. In this case, as imposed by the model setup (i.e., a single discontinuity), the southwestern margin is not perfectly rectilinear, and so models only partly fit with the natural case. Furthermore, some authors (e.g., García-Palomo et al., 2018) suggest that regional faults affect the substrate but also the surface in some locations. It is therefore possible that at LH regional structures affect, at least partly, the overburden (with the surface evidence being hidden by the volcano-clastic deposits). For this reason, the LH complex may be more similar to the setting tested by Model SODCC-2, which included two substrate to overburden IDs (Fig. 15h). This model shows straightforward similarities with the natural prototype. The geometry of two sub-orthogonal caldera ring faults is well reproduced and may support that the reactivation as normal faults of two inherited faults during the collapse may have influenced the LH structural pattern. The results of the modelling also allow us to speculate about the internal setting of the LH caldera before LPC development. In particular, the presence of these two substrate to overburden discontinuities may suggest that at LH, according to model SODCC-2, the outward-dipping reverse faults in correspondence of the two IDs may not only be masked by the LPC, but may be even missing. Nonetheless, reverse faults may be present in the northern portion of the collapsed caldera.

The above discussion suggests that inherited discontinuities can be reactivated during the caldera collapse. Considering that at LH and in other caldera collapse settings (e.g., Martí et al., 2008; Giordano et al. 2014; Norini et al., 2015, 2019; Garden et al. 2017; Liotta and WP4 Working Group, 2019; Montanari et al. 2017a; Jentsch et al., 2020) caldera structures are considered to bear a potential for favouring the upward migration of hydrothermal fluids, we speculate that these reactivated structures may behave in a similar manner. Besides, the presence/lack of caldera-related structures due to the possible inhibition induced by inherited fault reactivation is a condition that may influence the degree of fracturation and consequently the secondary permeability and fluid flow inside the caldera complex, therefore strongly affecting the geothermal potential.

Acoculco caldera complex

The Acoculco caldera complex (AC) lays ~80 km NW of LH (Fig. 15a), close to the western Apan-Tezontepec volcanic field (e.g., García-Tovar et al., 2015). North and east of AC, Cretaceous limestones of the Sierra Madre Occidental (Avellán et al., 2018) outcrop, while the caldera is bounded to the south by volcano-clastic deposits of the TMVB Avellán et al. (2020). López-Hernández (2009) suggested that the 15 km-wide AC (active from ≈ 1.7 to ≈ 0.2 Ma.) is nested inside the larger Tulancingo Caldera (active between between ≈ 3.0 and ≈ 2.7 Ma). Besides, Avellán et al. (2020) suggest that the caldera resulting of a 127 km^3 of andesitic ignimbrite eruption (the so called Acoculco unit) has been active between ≈ 2.7 to 0.06 Ma. Interestingly, these authors reported evidence of a regional structural control that may have been responsible for the present caldera geometry. In particular, NE-SW and NW-SE fault systems (Fig. 15d) may have controlled the collapse of the south-western, western and north-western sectors, connected by newly formed ring fault branches. This model is in agreement with what proposed by García-Palomo et al. (2018), who showed evidence of Pliocene-Quaternary extension in the area, responsible for the development of NE-SW structural trends. After caldera collapse, lacustrine sediments and post-caldera volcanic domes and lava flows partly filled the caldera depression (Avellán et al., 2020).

As for the LH caldera, the Acoculco caldera complex can be compared with some of our models. The better fit could again be with model SODCC-2 (Fig. 15h), which incorporates two substrate to overburden IDs. Inherited structures would therefore represent discrete faults extending from the substrate through the overburden and delimiting the magma chamber. The presence of two

rectilinear model discontinuities during the caldera collapse fits well with the hypothesis of regional structural control proposed by Avellán et al. (2020), and their reactivation has produced sharp rectilinear ring faults similar to those observed at the AC.

Figure 14. (a) South-eastern sector of the Trans-Mexican Volcanic belt (TMVB) shown in (b) illustrating the regional setting of the Los Humeros (LH) and Acoculco (AC) caldera complexes. Structures are simplified from Avellán et al. (2019); García-Palomo et al. (2018) and Norini et al. (2019). Orange dots in (a) show historical earthquakes (time interval 1900-2020) and relative magnitude for earthquakes with $M \geq 3$ (from USGS Earthquake Catalogue available at <https://www.usgs.gov/natural-hazards/earthquake-hazards/earthquakes>). (c) Local-scale structural setting of the Los Humeros caldera, and its nested Los Potreros caldera (LPC). Dashed black lines indicate inferred regional structures. Caldera structures are mapped after Carrasco-Núñez et al., 2017. (d) Structural setting of the Acoculco caldera complex. Structures are redrawn after Avellán et al., 2019, 2020. (e to h) Caldera collapse models with line-drawing of

structures superimposed from series SDCC and SODCC to which LH and AC can be compared. Models have been rotated 45° and 135° clockwise to fit with the two natural cases. Both the LH and AC case studies show straightforward similarities with Model SODCC-2, in which two substrate-to-overburden rectilinear inherited structures are reactivated during the collapse. Black tick arrows mark the similarities between nature (c, d) and the model (h).

These authors also suggest the possible interaction between inherited structures and the caldera collapse process. However, our models suggest that no differences occur in the process when having one or two IDs, and it is probably the same when there are more IDs. It is therefore likely that the presence of other discontinuities may simply produce further rectilinear caldera rims. The limitations adopted for the LH comparison remains valid. Also in this case, draping sediments (both lacustrine and volcanic) hide the caldera-collapse-related inner structures, and thus it is not possible to compare the intra-caldera structures with our models. Nonetheless, as for the LH we speculate that the presence of substrate to overburden discontinuities may have inhibited the formation of inner outward-dipping normal faults in correspondence of the inherited structures (see model SODCC-2).

5.2.2. The Tuscolano-Artemisio Caldera (Colli Albani volcanic district)

The Colli Albani (Latium, Italy, Fig. 16a) are a quiescent Quaternary volcanic complex mainly active between 0.6-0.2 Ma (De Rita et al., 1995), and are part of the NW-trending, K-alkaline, peri-Tyrrhenian volcanic belt, resulting from magma emplacement in a back-arc extensional context (Conticelli and Peccerillo, 1992, Foley and Peccerillo, 1992). The Colli Albani derived from the multiphase eruptive activity (that mainly produced leucititic magmas) and the associated collapse of several superimposed volcanic edifices. Specifically, four volcanic edifices (some of these composites, i.e., deriving from multiple associated emission points) are recognised at the Colli Albani (Giordano et al., 2006), from older to younger: the Vulcano Laziale, the Tuscolano-Artemisio, the Faete and the Via dei Laghi edifices. The most prominent morphologic evidence of a caldera collapse in the area is marked by the Tuscolano-Artemisio (TA) peri-caldera composite edifices (Fig. 16a), a series of emission points associated with the main caldera rims generated during the collapse of the Vulcano Laziale edifice, produced by the so-called Villa Senni eruption (355 ka, Giordano et al., 2006). The ~ 8 x 8 km TA caldera is marked by a sharp NE-SW trending margin (the so-called Artemisio segment) and by a more rounded NW-SE caldera rim highlighted by the Tuscolano-Artemisio (TA) peri-caldera composite edifice. The latter was emplaced along the

caldera rim during non-explosive phases of the caldera collapse and covering, at the time of the formation, a morphologically stable caldera wall (Giordano et al., 2006). On the SW margin, several maars and smaller eruptive centres (Fig. 16a) appear aligned along a regional tectonic structure. Several authors have, in fact, suggested that the geometry of this volcanic district has been shaped by tectonic structures in the substrate (e.g. Funiciello and Parotto, 1978; Rosa, 1995; De Rita et al., 1995). Overall, the Colli Albani are emplaced at the intersection between NW-SE and NE-SW systems of tectonic structures (Fig. 16a), which intersect with N-S dextral faults (e.g., De Rita et al., 1995; Acocella & Funiciello, 2006) and may have also controlled the collapse of some nested calderas in the area, including the TA caldera.

Overall, the structural setting of the Colli Albani volcanic district is similar to the two Mexican case studies, in which a poly-phased volcanic complex is emplaced on inherited tectonic structures, which intersect with a sub-orthogonal trend and that have likely controlled the localization of the magmatic source and the consequent caldera collapse. We can therefore compare the TA caldera with the same models used for the Mexican comparison, particularly models from both SDCC and SODCC series. As for the Los Humeros and Acahualtlan calderas, it is more reasonable to compare the TA caldera with SODCC models, owing to the presence of substrate to overburden inherited discontinuities. We can therefore compare Model SODCC-1 (single ID; Fig. 16b) and model SODCC-2 (two IDs; Fig. 16c) with the morphology-tectonic of the natural case, highlighting again a straightforward similarity. In particular, the curved NW-SE trending caldera margin and the rectilinear NE-SW trending Artemisa sectors are strikingly similar to the geometry produced by our models, supporting again that inherited structures have the ability to produce sharp morphology and interact with the caldera collapse. Furthermore, the SW caldera margin is nowadays obliterated by aligned maars and volcanic edifices associated with younger (≈ 200 ka-Holocene) volcanic edifices (i.e., the Via dei Laghi edifice; Giordano et al., 2006). This setting may indicate that tectonic structures are able to maintain over time their structural control on the caldera complex, inherited structures being also exploited by post-caldera collapse activity. This SW margin seems, in fact, localized along a regional structure (Fig. 16a), supporting our initial choice of model SODCC-2 as a best fit for the comparison with the natural prototype.

Figure 16. (a) The Colli Albani volcanic district with the Tuscolano-Artemisio Caldera. Structures are redrawn after Acocella & Funicello (2006) and Giordano et al. (2006). Orange dots in (a) show historical earthquakes (time interval 1900–2020) with $M \geq 3$ (from the USGS Earthquake Catalogue available at <https://www.usgs.gov/natural-hazards/earthquake-hazards/earthquakes>). (b) and (c), Analogue models with superimposed DEM and line-drawing of structures from series SODCC, to be compared with the Tuscolano-Artemisio Caldera. Models have been rotated 45° and 135° clockwise to fit with the natural case study. Black thick arrows mark possible similarities between nature (a) and the models (b,c).

5.2.3. The Glencoe Caldera

Since the time of the first description (Clough et al., 1909), the Caledonian Glencoe Caldera (Scotland, Fig. 17a,b) has represented a favourable site for the exploration of caldera structures, as this deeply eroded collapsed caldera allows to access structures and deposits commonly obscured in many younger caldera settings. Particularly, ring faults were firstly documented at this site by Clough et al. (1909) who originally suggested a piston-like collapse model for this caldera. Later on, it has been deeply investigated (e.g., Moore & Kokelaar, 1997, 1998; Roberts, 1974; Kokelaar & Moore, 2006; Kokelaar, 2007) and used as an analogue for comparison with other calderas (e.g., Moore & Kokelaar, 1998, and references therein; McCall, 1963; Acocella, 2007; Branney & Acocella, 2015), as well as with analogue models (e.g., Holohan et al., 2008a). Other authors

suggested an asymmetric caldera collapse model for the Glencoe Caldera (Roberts, 1974), even though a different process was envisaged by Moore & Kokelaar (1997, 1998) who documented how active regional structures interacted with caldera collapse generating an incoherent (i.e., fragmented in blocks) subsidence of the caldera floor, ultimately leading to piecemeal caldera collapse. Above the late Precambrian to early Paleozoic metamorphic basement, these Authors described in detail five major caldera-forming eruptions (producing rhyolite ignimbrites) that partly reactivated regional structures inside the ring fault system. Specifically, a system of orthogonally-intersecting NW-SE trending faults (namely, the North-western and South-eastern Graben Faults) and SW-NE faults (i.e., the Ossian, the Queen's Cairn, the Devil's Staircase, the Glen Etive and the White Corries faults) dissected the caldera collapse subsided block (Moore & Kokelaar, 1997, 1998) creating grabens. Such orthogonal grabens (Fig. 17a) recorded extension and/or transtension associated with the Glencoe Lineament and the Etive-Laggan Faults (Fig. 17b). The multiphase and repeated magma plumbing below the graben system indicates that magma ascent was likely favoured by the presence of basement structures and concurrent tectonic activity (Moore & Kokelaar, 1997). Moore & Kokelaar (1998) suggested that these pre-existing structures were likely activated by nearby regional strike-slip structures (i.e., the Great Glean Fault and the Highland Boundary faults, Fig.17b). These authors documented active tectonism describing seven cycles of incision and fluvial/lacustrine sedimentation as well as deposition of megabreccias originated by fault scarp degradation and alluvial fan progradation occurring during magmatic stasis or concurrent with volcanic activity. This evolution resulted in a complex piecemeal caldera setting, afterward partly obliterated by post-caldera granite intrusion (i.e., Cruachan Granite, Moore & Kokelaar, 1997; Fig. 17a). The Glencoe Caldera represents the locus of concurrent interaction of caldera collapse and tectonics processes, and is therefore worth of comparison with our models. Notably, some limitations arise when approaching this comparison, namely: 1) our models reproduced piston-like caldera collapse, and therefore they do not strikingly simulate the piecemeal architecture described at Glencoe, the latter resulting from 2) the concurrent effect of active tectonics and volcanism. Our models simulate the reactivation of inherited structures without taking into account the effect of active regional tectonics during caldera development. Despite this limitation, a comparison can be attempted with our models of ODCC experimental series, which reproduced the case of a magma chamber emplaced at crustal levels interacting with structures in the overlaying overburden, and thus not delimiting the magma chamber itself, as it is instead the case of the Glencoe Caldera. In this natural prototype, ring faults

assumed in fact a curvilinear (elliptical) geometry and do not seem to have been controlled by inherited structures (yet, the elongation of the collapse can be attributed to the control exerted by the NW-SE-trending structural alignment of the Glencoe Lineament; Fig. 17a,b). This inference justifies the comparison with the ODCC series, rather than with the others. Specifically, the intra-caldera structures described at Glencoe can be compared with the overburden discontinuity of model ODCC-1 (Fig. 17c), which was reactivated as a rectilinear feature during the collapse. Furthermore, as described above, such a reactivation does not inhibit the propagation of circular (or elliptical, in the case of Glencoe Caldera) ring faults that are free to assume the classical cylindrical or truncated-cone shape. The reactivated discontinuity may be therefore strikingly compared with the North-eastern or South-eastern Graben faults, or with the orthogonally intersecting faults bounding cross-grabens (Fig. 17a).

Figure 17. (a) The Glencoe Caldera (Scotland) and its structural setting (b). Structures in (a, b) are redrawn from Moore and Kokelaar (1997, 1998) and Kokelaar (2007). GGF: Great Glen Fault; GL: Glencoe Lineament; CL: Cruachan Lineament; Etlf: Etive-Laggan Fault; ErLF: Ericht-Laidon Fault. The red line indicates the Glencoe Caldera ring faults. Orange thick dashed lines mark tectonic lineaments active at the time of Glencoe collapse. (c) The inherited overburden discontinuity in Model ODCC-1 can be compared with some of the reactivated intra-caldera structures at Glencoe. Black and blue thick arrows mark possible similarities respectively between reactivated structures and ring faults in (a) nature and (c) in the model.

Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that some of the reactivated structures are located in a central position in the Glencoe Caldera (e.g., the Devil's Staircase Fault runs closely to the caldera minor axis, Fig. 17a). Despite that our model testing an overburden central discontinuity (Model ODCC-2) indicates that such a structure is likely not reactivated - in line with the results from Holohan et al. (2008a) - Moore & Kokelaar (1997, 1998) suggested that this structure accommodated part of the collapse displacement at Glencoe. Holohan et al. (2008a), basing on their laboratory experiments, discussed this possible discrepancy according to three modelling factors, which are in common with our models, particularly: 1) low caldera floor thickness/diameter ratio and a flat top-surface of the magma chamber, which would not favour fragmentation (and hence reactivation of inherited structures); 2) a single collapse (multiple cycles of collapse are likely to induce larger caldera floor fragmentation), and 3) a single magma chamber (multilevel and locally active chambers may contribute to fragmentation). Furthermore, active tectonics may certainly contribute to caldera block formation and structure reactivation. These modelling factors basically reflect the assumption of our modelling approach, which simulates a non-repeated cylindrical collapse of a single-magma chamber, leading to piston-like calderas. These aspects should therefore be taken into specific account when trying to model complex multiphase piecemeal caldera collapse occurring in active tectonic settings.

6. Conclusive remarks

We performed analogue models to investigate fault propagation in caldera collapse systems, and their interaction with inherited upper crustal discontinuities, which were proven to strongly influence the final structural deformation pattern. Our main findings are summarised below:

- 1) Our standard caldera collapse model bears first-order similarity with many of the underpressure analogue models available in literature, showing the presence of inward-dipping reverse faults and outward-dipping normal faults, unless this standard evolution is perturbed by the presence of reactivated inherited structures.
- 2) Despite this first order similarity, our models showed how symmetric calderas can experience asymmetry due to lateral propagation of caldera structures, which are able to produce peculiar structural patterns (i.e., x-pattern) that may accommodate some strike-slip component of movement, as already observed in previous studies. Furthermore, the presence of inherited

discontinuities may force the caldera collapse process to diverge from the standard model evolution, originating different structural patterns.

3) Inherited discontinuities can induce variations on the evolution of the caldera structural pattern, therefore differentiating it from the standard model. Specifically, inherited discontinuities delimiting the analogue magma chamber can produce rectilinear caldera faults at surface, generating non-circular ring faults. In addition, substrate discontinuities can produce rectilinear intra-caldera structures that do not affect the caldera rims. Finally, sub-vertical substrate-to-overburden discontinuities may be able to generate not only rectilinear ring faults, but also to inhibit the formation of outward-dipping reverse faults in some intra-caldera sectors.

4) Overall, the models performed with various combinations of one, two discontinuities resulted in a complex structural pattern. The comparison with natural cases can improve our understanding of caldera systems that do not show circular shapes and a classical ring-fault evolution. In addition, the results of the modelling can help to interpret the development of intra-caldera structures, which are often hidden below pyroclastic caldera deposits.

5) When compared with specific natural cases (i.e., the Los Humeros and the Acoculco caldera complexes in Mexico, the Tuscolano-Aremisio caldera in the Colli Albani volcanic district, Italy) our models may explain some peculiar structural patterns (e.g., rectilinear ring faults), contributing to shed some light on the evolution of caldera complexes.

6) Comparison with the Glencoe Caldera, Scotland, showed that, despite possible similarities, simple analogue models (single piston-like collapse induced by emptying of a single magma chamber) fail to explain part of the structural variability observed at piecemeal-caldera collapse. In this regard, as already suggested by other Authors (Holohan et al., 2008a) the implementation of analogue models involving the collapse of multiple magma chambers inducing multiphase collapse should be taken into consideration.

7) Finally, our results may provide useful hints for geothermal exploration, as caldera-related structures may localise fluid flow (geothermal as well as meteoric/recharge), and consequently become important exploration targets.

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Highlights

- We modelled caldera collapse interacting with inherited structures
- Models show how inherited structures change classical evolution of caldera collapse
- Specific caldera structures are inhibited by reactivation of inherited structures
- We compare models to the Los Humeros, Acoculco, Colli Albani and Glencoe calderas
- Models show that these calderas strongly interacted with inherited structures

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Credit Author Statement

Daniele Maestrelli: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; **Marco Bonini:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Resources, Supervision. **Giacomo Corti:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing; **Chiara Del Ventisette:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; **Giovanna Moratti:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; **Domenico Montanari:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; Resources, Supervision.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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